

A New Mode of Geothermal Development for Africa: the “Geothermal Village” Concept

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ABSTRACT

Africa - in particular all along the East African Rift System (EARS) - has geothermal resources of high value (shallow volcano-tectonic related). Kenya now relies on large-size geothermal plants to ensure its electric baseload. Nevertheless, the resource – even if exceptional with steam available at the surface - is essentially untapped, particularly in the remote and arid areas where the societal needs are highest. This due largely to a lack of reference (demonstration) projects when relatively inexpensive boreholes can tap quite hot fluids (up to 150°C). The *Geothermal Village* concept relies upon geothermal fluids obtained from moderate depth boreholes, used first for small-size electricity production then in a cascade of increasingly lower temperature for direct use (DU) such as drying crops/fish/meat, cooking and baking, fish farms and greenhouses, pasteurizing, bathing and washing, cooling and freezing, and hot bath. First investigations show that hundreds of sites along the EARS have the resources appropriate for such developments, each installation allowing modular expansion. But R&D (producing know-how) is required to implement the solutions at the local level, as the nature of the resource and of the energy demand significantly differs from existing scheme. The present project, supported by the EU-AU LEAP-RE program mobilize interdisciplinary teams from both Europe and Africa to develop a few relevant demonstration systems, adapted to the specific socio-economic needs of the local community, at an appropriate technology level. It implies geoscientific and social sciences research, the development of appropriate technologies, engineering, and capacity building in both technologies and socio-economics. Conceptual, engineering and physical tools are being developed to support community-based initiatives and local capabilities, working through schools, universities, public and private entities, cooperatives CBOs and NGOs. The ambition is to create in Africa the capacities to master the whole value chain of basic knowledge, technology management, social organizations and economic capabilities to ensure the maintenance, extension and replication of such community-based projects. The first step is identifying sites, characterizing them, and arriving at a generic energy-system plan. The second step is site feasibility and design. The third step, for which additional support is looked for, will be the construction of demonstrator systems for 3 selected “Geothermal Village” sites. With model plans for high enthalpy (HE) sites in the Eastern Rift and Afar, and medium-enthalpy (ME) site in the W & S Rifts, representing also the variation in societal context, where the requirements of pastoral indigenous, fishing or agricultural communities each imply a different use of the resource. The paper describes the work being engaged on the 4 sites including geosciences and social sciences, and the general time-frame of the project in the 3 years period 2021-2023.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Research and Development (R&D) project called “Geothermal Village 1” (GV1) was granted 950.000 Euros for a 3 year period by the EU research programme called “Long-Term Joint European Union - African Union Research and Innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy” (LEAP-RE). This project aims at developing renewable energy solutions for Africa. The objective of GV1 is to introduce geothermal-based stand-alone electric and thermal energy systems to African communities located off -grid, providing template case-studies on adapting the energy systems to community needs, choosing sites with different thermal and socio-economic characteristics representative of the diversity of situations along the EARV, and developing for each site a suitable energy plan. Aiming to keep the technology level appropriate to local operation, maintenance and replication, with the long-term objective of capacity development, economic and social welfare, and encourage young educated people to stay on their homeland. These systems will empower women and girls by: (i) supplying fresh water and (ii) clean cooking solutions by supplanting oil and firewood. This in turn contribute to environmental and health benefits as well as reduces the domestic expense and workload on women and girls allowing time for education and productivity. It also addresses climate resilience, and developing capacities at the individual and institutional levels to engage modular developments and to adapt to further changes. This GV1 project is built jointly by European and African partners from academia, public institutions, community-based organizations (CBOs) and private partners already involved in the EARS domain and experienced in Euro-African partnership.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT

2.1 The Euro-African Team engaged in the Project

The partners have solid and complementary experience in the region and geothermal R&D. The project follows the concept Geothermal Village elaborated with Omenda et al. (2014) applied in the Geopower Africa Project (2013-2017) supported by USAID and US academies, and the recent IRENA survey. As a result, civil society organizations were created, specialized SMEs mobilized and sustained partnership developed with specialized public institutions now part of this project. Participants include: University of Lorraine (Y Géraud coordinating) and University of Western Brittany (P. Tarits), Università degli Studi di Torino (A. Sciullo), Sant’Anna School of Adv. Studies (M. Contini), Fraunhofer Inst. for Energy Infrastr. & Geoth. Systems (I. Nardini), NORCE (Norway; W.H. Wheeler), Ressources Géologiques pour le Développement Durable (S. Onyango, & J. Varet), Energy Development Corporation Ltd, Rwanda (U. Rutagarama), Addis Ababa University (B. Atnafu), University of Nairobi, Kenya (W. Mitullah and J. Onjala), Office Djiboutien de Devt. de la Géothermie (K. Moussa), Scientific & Engineering Power Consultants, Kenya (P. Omenda), Afar Geothermal Alternative Power Co., Ethiopia (I. A. Gardo) and Homa Hills Geothermal Community Based Org., Kenya (Z. Change).

2.2 Looking for a new kind of Geothermal Energy Development in Africa

Geothermal is a flexible, full-time energy source that allows to answer local needs and serve surroundings through energy and water networks. With the objective to introduce stand-alone electric and thermal energy an African-European R&D group was built (see participants above) aiming to provide template case-studies adapting geothermal energy resource and off-grid systems to community needs in Africa in four selected countries representative of the diversity of situations encountered, namely, Ethiopia, Kenya, Djibouti, Rwanda. After field studies already engaged, sites with different thermal and socio-economic characteristics were selected, developing for each an adapted research program, aiming at a suitable energy plan. The technology level will be appropriate to local operation, maintenance and replication, which furthers the long-term objective of capacity building, economic and social welfare; encouraging young educated people to stay on their homeland. These systems are conceived to supply fresh water and supplant oil and firewood which,

in addition to environmental and health benefits, reduces the domestic expense and workload on women and girls allowing time for education and productivity. They directly address most if not all objectives and roadmaps of sustainable development including access to water and clean energy, climate resilience; developing capacities at individual and institutional levels to engage modular developments and to adapt to further changes, through smart grid, off grid, stand-alone systems and processes and appliances for productive uses.

2.3 Background and Concept

Africa - in particular all along the East African Rift System (EARS, Figure 1) and the Cameroon line - has geothermal resources of high value, shallow volcano-tectonic related (Omenda et al 2016, Gardo and Varet, 2018, Rutagarama and Varet, 2018). Kenya now relies on large-size geothermal plants to ensure its electric baseload. Nevertheless, the resource – even if exceptional with steam available at the surface (Figure 2) - is essentially untapped, particularly in the remote and arid areas where the societal needs are highest. In these areas, the energy and water issue is essentially handled by women and girls. Geothermal resources are known but only tapped through artisanal devices, mainly by steam condensation (Gardo and Varet, 2020 & Figure 3) This due largely to a lack of reference (demonstration) projects when relatively inexpensive boreholes can tap quite hot fluids (150°C), sufficient for electricity and many domestic, agricultural and industrial processes. R&D (producing know-how) is required to implement at the local organization level, African solutions as the nature of the resource and of the energy demand significantly differs from elsewhere (Varet et al. 2014, Onyango and Varet, 2018). The Geothermal Village concept is illustrated in Figure 4. Geothermal fluid obtained from moderate-depth boreholes is used first for electricity (through ORC solutions) then in a cascade of increasingly lower temperature for direct uses (DU) such as drying crops/fish/meat, cooking and baking, fish farms and greenhouses, pasteurizing (dairy), pottery and brick kilns, timber, Varet et al. - GV1 3 bathing and washing, supply drinking water, and even provide cooling and freezing, including eco-tourism based on hot-springs resorts run by the local population. First investigations (Mariita et al. 2016) show that hundreds of sites along the EARS have geothermal resources appropriate for such developments.

Figure 1: Map showing the EARS (East African Rift System) along which the geothermal resource is located. Geothermal sites are found along active faults (in red) and active volcanic systems (yellow). Map from Calais (2016) showing the plate motions (in mmm/y) within the African continent, which govern the active geothermal systems found all along the different branches of the EARS, from Malawi to Afar. All along these geodynamic structures, there are places for local geothermal project allowing for cascade use of the energy and of the water produced by relatively shallow and therefore rather economic systems.

Figure 2.: Steam vents along a fault affecting basaltic rocks in central Afar (Ethiopia), a kind of manifestation that is quite frequent along the East African Rift Valley. (Photo J.Varet).

Figure 3: All along the EARV, various kinds of artisanal devices are traditionally used to tap the geothermal steam at the surface for domestic uses, mainly liquid water production answering human and herds needs (Era Boru, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia).

Figure 4: Scheme of the geothermal village concept with production of geothermal fluids from shallow depths intersecting feeding geological structures of the surface manifestations, and cascade use with electricity and cascade direct uses (Varet et al., 2014).

2.4 Aims of the GVI project

The geothermal resource needs appropriate geoscientific solutions for a precise 3D mapping of the “plumbing system” of the fluids, whereas the anthropological study of the social demand allow to determine the best-suited kind of cascade uses to be implemented through the most adapted technological solutions. Based on interdisciplinary research, the project will allow to develop a few relevant systems, adapted to the specific socio-economic needs of the local community, at an appropriate technology level. It requires geoscientific and social sciences research, the development of appropriate technologies, engineering, and capacity building in both technologies and socio-economics (Onyango and Varet 2018). European and African entities listed in 2.1 jointly engaged in this 3-years (2021-2023) in order to develop the conceptual, engineering and physical tools to support community-based initiatives and develop local capabilities, working through schools, universities, public and private entities, cooperatives CBOs and NGOs (Onyango and Varet, 2016). The ambition is to create in Africa the capacities to master the whole chain of basic knowledge, technology management, social organizations and economic capabilities to ensure the maintenance, extension and replication of such community-based geothermal projects. Since the Geothermal Village concept was conceived, civil society organizations were created, SMEs and public research partners mobilized, and sustained partnership developed with specialized public institutions now part of this project (HHCBO, AGAP, ODDEG, EDCL among other).

Figure 5: Vote of the status and of community representatives for the Afar Geothermal Alternative Power Company (AGAP) at Ab’Ala (Afar Regional State, Ethiopia). Photo J.Varet, January 2015.

3. METHODOLOGY AND WORK PLAN

The first step is identifying sites, characterizing them, and arriving at a generic energy-system plan. All these have technical and social elements. The second step is site feasibility and design. The third step, for which additional support is looked for, will be the construction of demonstrator systems for which 3 suitable “Geothermal Village” sites will be selected from the EARS. With model plans for high-enthalpy (HE) sites in the Eastern Rift and Afar, and medium-enthalpy (ME) site in the W & S Rifts, (Omenda et al. 2016) representing also the variation in societal context, where the requirements of pastoral indigenous, fishing or agricultural communities each imply a different use of the electricity and thermal water.

3.1 First step

In the first step:

- *Geosciences* focuses on developing appropriate methods to efficiently identify and drill into the hot geothermal fluids at depths of 300 to 1000 m. integrating geology, geochemistry, and geophysics for high-resolution 3D models of the underground plumbing systems of the hydrothermally active, fractured areas (1 km³ models) ;
- *Social sciences* aim to understand the traditional social organization, gender dimension including societal roles (women and girls tasked with water and energy supply Onyango and Varet, 2014; Mariita et al. 2016), traditional economies and interest in geothermal technologies, and develop the knowledge, awareness and appropriation by local communities through anthropological and sociological approaches Onyango and Varet, 2016). Strategies and models for effective communities' engagement will be explored;
- *Engineering* will identify, select and adapt ad-hoc African technologies and local engineering solutions to high temperature shallow drilling and production and handling the geothermal fluids (pipes, heat exchangers, and condensing systems) for the ORC and direct use (DU) cascade devices - in most cases furnished by a few specialized subcontracting SMEs – and further match these to the needs of pastoral, fishing and agricultural communities.

3.2 Second step

The second step will allow to establish the feasibility of the specific sites with respect to the above results. The feasibility of community-based approaches will be assessed in terms of project design, stakeholders' and communities' engagement, and medium-long term sustainability of the project, in terms of potential business model for spread the technical solution. It will establish the social and technical knowledge to plan the demonstrators for *GV Phase 2* and related capacity building. Staff mobility, capacity building, and project management will be specifically addressed.

3.3 Third step

Towards the third step, the implementation of demonstration projects, the consortium aims to obtain funding by year two, so that the demonstrator(s) can seamlessly follow this project.

3.4 Research mobility & partnership

- Involvement of Master and PhD students in the project
- Summer schools/workshops about RE, in synergy and coordination with the other LEAP-RE WPs

3.5 Capacity building

- Based on needs assessments, training for local communities *to ensure proper mastering of the whole chain* of basic knowledge (from technology and financial handling to administrative and social management)
- This should guarantee maintenance, extension and replication of such community-based geothermal projects.
- Trainings through CBOs and NGOs involved in the GV (e.g. Kenya: HHCBO ; Ethiopia: AGAP)

3.6 Work plan

The Work Plan is based on 3 years detailed programs, with well-defined tasks a sub-tasks assigned to each partner, always based on afro-European partnerships (Fig. 6). The results of the R&D engaged in first year will have provided the necessary data for engaging the detailed feasibility studies on the sites selected for their relevance to the diversity of the geological and of the social situations encountered. A joint feasibility frame will be defined and will be applied in selected sites

each of the 4 countries also involving specialized technical partners depending on the DU options considered. This will be followed by definition of proper legal framework (community-based enterprise, cooperative, “société d’économie mixte”, public-private partnership...), financial arrangement (stakeholders own funds, grants, soft loans...) allowing for the project’s implementation, including the process of payment by consumers ensuring the sustainable management of the whole device.

Figure 6: Time frame and work packages (WP) for GV1. D: deliverables. C: meetings & decision points.

4.0 THE FOUR SITES SELECTED

Four (4) sites were selected in the 4 participating African Countries: Ethiopia, Djibouti, Rwanda and Kenya

4.1 Era Boru, Afar Regional State, Ethiopia

Geographic Coordinates: 12°40’N – 40°20’ E; Altitude: 700m (see map Figure 7)

Surface thermal manifestations are numerous (steam vents) and well known by the Afar pastors, as they are artisanal engineered to condensate the steam and produce water that is used for both livestock’s and human consumption:

- digging holes in the fumarole site,
- use the clay (red kaolin-iron hydroxides mixtures) produced by the hydrothermal decomposition of the volcanic rock to create an impermeable basin for condensate water collection,
- close the system with a chimney made of blocks of lava covered by branches (acacias trees) that will allow to condensate the steam (as in condensation towers of thermal plants).

Example of such devices, are quite common all over Afar particularly at Era Boru where 150 families live from this resource. The project should allow to identify shallow drilling targets and answer the needs of the communities on site (energy through portable ORC and water production by steam condensation). It was however delayed due to safety conditions. We still hope to be able to engage the geosciences and social sciences field work in the year 2022.

Fig. 7: Geological map of central-eastern Afar showing the location of Era Boru site (red rectangle) in the accommodation (leaky transform fault) zone between Alayta and Manda Harraro axial ranges (spreading segment). See Varet et al. (2020) for precisions.

4.2 Djibouti Republic, Lac Abhé

Geographic Coordinates: 11°09'16 N; 41°53'00 E Altitude: 245-313 m

The project is the most advanced on this site, with successful geosciences field work in the Lac Abhé area (Oct. – Nov. 2021), with the active participation of ODDEG.

Geosciences:

- Geology including drone survey (Figure 8)
- Geochemistry, of gases in particular
- Geophysics (high resolution MT providing detailed 3D resistivity models in the 1Km³ volume)
- Characterization of the potential drilling site and of the geothermal reservoir
- Synthesis of data processing with all the involved partners

Fig. 8: Geothermal travertine chimneys: Infra-Red drone survey (left) and oblique view (right).

Social sciences: Preliminary survey

- 70 families near the site;
- a school just built and started operating
- More families will join the village that the geothermal resource will power,
- also providing water

The detailed social study will be engaged in the coming months 2022.

4.3. Homa Hills, E. Lake Victoria, Kenya

Geographic Coordinates: 0°20'20 N; 34°31' E. Altitude: 1131-1180 m

Previous investigations confirmed:

- Low to intermediate temperature geothermal system in the prospect.
- Heat source associated with magmatic intrusive.
- Estimated reservoir geothermometry from 160°C to 235°C.
- A resource to be utilized both for electricity generation and direct uses (crops & fish drying, hot bath).

Field works (geoscience and social sciences) engaged in March 2022

- Structural geology, geochemistry geophysics (high resolution MT) allowing to establish a 3D picture of the hydrothermal system plumbing at 1 Km³ scale (data processing under progress).
- Anthropological study & analysis of the local socio-economic demand (present and future) being quantified, in partnership with the local community (with HHCBO).

Fig. 9: The Homa Hills carbonatite massif: Abundu geothermal site (photo J. Varet)

Fig. 10: Fishing in Lake Victoria at Homa Hills near the geothermal site (Photo J. Varet)

4.4 Mashyuza Bugarama District, southern Rwanda

Coordinates: 2°42' S; 25°01 E. Altitude: 956m Access (distance & time): 260 km from Kigali, 6 hours' drive. Bugarama district, in southern Rwanda, near the Burundi and RDC borders, is rather rich in thermal manifestations (Fig.11). At least 3 sites are gifted with hot springs, with characteristics not suitable for electricity production. One of them has selected in the frame of GV project in May 2022 (Omenda & Varet, internal report)

Given the local economy based on agriculture, Direct Uses (DU) are the only possible kind of geothermal applications in the area. But given the importance of the outflow at Mashyuza, these could be significant contributions to the local economy. Identified applications include crop (in particular rice, tea, vegetable and fruits) drying, fish farming and drying, limestone pre-heating for cement processing and thermal bath and SPAs.

Although already well studied, complementary exploration works are being planned with EDCL in mid- 2022, implying both earth science and social science teams, followed by technology assessments. This site opens perspectives for similar developments in other sites in the region and the demonstration will also be of use for the whole western branch and southern part of the EARS.

Fig. 11: regional map of southern Rwanda showing the Bugarama corridor, an accommodation zone between the Kivu and Tanganyika rifts. Mashyuza site location is indicated by the red square.

5.0 CONCLUSION

Given the exceptional geological characteristics along the EARS, and the rising needs of the people living there - eventually increasingly affected by climate change which induces necessary social changes - time has come to really allow for geothermal development to popularise in the African continent. After a few years of conceptual work, and attempts to develop projects allowing for geothermal energy to serve the needs of the communities on site where the resource is available near the surface, a Euro-African team was formed to develop the necessary research in order to finally establish on a few demonstration sites the *Geothermal Village* concept. This paper not only accounts for the program now in progress but is also a call for increased partnership - through GAK and other regional professional associations in particular – for a successful development and duplication of such locally-based sustainable, climate resilient solutions.

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